

**SHIELDING EFFECTIVENESS MEASUREMENTS
FOR AN SHF/EHF FIELD-TO-WIRE COUPLING MODEL**

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The Intrasystem Electromagnetic Compatibility Analysis Program (IEMCAP) is a widely used code for EMC modeling. IEMCAP includes a coupling model for an external field incident on a wire over a ground plane (field-to-wire model). In an effort to expand the capability of IEMCAP in the SHF/EHF region, the frequency range of the field-to-wire model was increased to 40 GHz. Since the field-to-wire model must account for shielded cables as well as bare wires, experiments were conducted in a mode-tuned reverberation chamber to measure the shielding effectiveness from 1 GHz to 40 GHz of various types of cables. A wide variety of experimental parameters were surveyed. These included cable type (coaxial cables, twisted pairs), shielding (single and double shields), cable length, termination impedance, and shield termination condition (circumferentially bonded shield, pigtail, ungrounded shield). Note that the shielding measurements were made well outside the normal operating region of the cables under test. The results of the experimental program support a shielding effectiveness model that is dependent on cable type and very sensitive to the existence of an exposed center conductor or pigtail.

Introduction

In order to extend the capabilities of the Intrasystem Electromagnetic Compatibility Analysis Program (IEMCAP) in the SHF/EHF region, a number of shielding effectiveness (S.E.) experiments were conducted in a mode-tuned reverberation chamber (MTRC). The purpose of the experiments was to determine what parameters most influence cable shielding from 1 GHz to 40 GHz, and to quantify those parameters in order to derive an empirical model for inclusion into IEMCAP [1]. It is important to note that the S.E. measurements were conducted at frequencies much higher than the normal operating frequencies of the cables under test.

A wide variety of experimental parameters was surveyed. These included cable type (coaxial cables, twisted pairs), shielding configuration (single and double shields), cable length, termination impedance, and shield termination condition (circumferentially bonded shield, pigtail, ungrounded shield). The experimental survey revealed that the cable type and shield termination condition were important. The primary variables for shield termination condition were whether the incident

field could couple directly onto the center conductor, and if so, how far away from the receiver port the coupling took place. Other parameters had little or no effect on S.E.

Test Configuration

All of the shielding effectiveness measurements were made in a mode-tuned reverberation chamber (MTRC) [2]. The MTRC is an over-moded resonant cavity with a large rotating paddle or stirrer inside it. As the paddle is rotated, the electromagnetic boundary conditions within the cavity are changed, causing a corresponding change in the electromagnetic field distribution. The MTRC for these experiments was 1.07 m x 1.19 m x 1.55 m with a lower frequency limit of about 250 MHz.

A block diagram of the test configuration is shown in Figure 1. Each test cable was placed in the MTRC with both ends of the cable attached to the chamber walls. Port 1 of a network analyzer was connected via semi-rigid coaxial cable to a microwave horn located inside the MTRC. Port 2 of the network analyzer was connected to one end of the test cable. The opposite end of the test cable was terminated in either an open, short, or 50 ohm load.

The S.E. for a given cable was determined by measuring the ratio of the power coupled to the test cable to the power radiated into the chamber. Using S-parameters this can be written as

$$P_c = S_{21} / (1 - S_{11})$$

where P_c is the ratio of coupled power to radiated power. This ratio was measured at 50 different paddle positions (hence 50 different distributions of electromagnetic power) and then averaged. After replacing the test cable with an unshielded reference wire, the measurement was repeated. By comparing the average ratio of coupled power for a test cable to the average ratio for a reference wire, cable shielding effectiveness was determined.

Test Results

Because the relevant factors that might affect S.E. were unknown at the beginning of the experimental phase, many different parameters were examined. Some cable parameters had little or no effect on S.E. For

Figure 1. Test Configuration for Shielding Effectiveness Measurements

example, the S.E. of single shielded and double shielded coaxial cables was measured from 1 GHz to 40 GHz for several different cable lengths. The measurements demonstrated that a change in cable length has no appreciable effect on S.E. Other cable parameters that had little effect on S.E. included cable termination impedance (open, short, or 50 ohm load) and pigtail length (if a pigtail was present).

The cable parameters having the greatest effect on S.E. were cable type (including type of shield) and shield termination condition. Figure 2 shows the measured S.E. of a single shielded coaxial cable (RG-58C/U) and a double shielded coaxial cable (RG-223/U) from 1 GHz to 40 GHz. As expected, the double shielded cable exhibits greater shielding effectiveness.

Figure 2. Measured Shielding Effectiveness for RG-58C/U and RG-223/U

IEMCAP Model

Shield termination condition refers to the manner in which the cable shield is physically attached to a connector or bulkhead. Generally, the shield can be either circumferentially bonded to a connector, attached to the connector with a pigtail, or left unattached. Note that in the last two cases the center conductor of the cable may be exposed to the direct electromagnetic fields.

If any portion of the center conductor is exposed, then the coupling to the cable is similar to that for a bare wire. However, the location of the exposed center conductor, relative to the port of interest, is important. If the exposed center conductor is at the receiver port, then the cable will exhibit no shielding. If the exposed center conductor is at a port away from the receiver, then the coupled power is attenuated as it propagates along the cable towards the receiver port. Figure 3 depicts this frequency dependent propagation loss for RG-58C/U and the smoothed model included in IEMCAP.

The shielding model derived for inclusion in IEMCAP accounts for both the shielding of the cable and the attenuation of the cable. IEMCAP first calculates the attenuation (S.E.) of coupled power due to a grounded, circumferentially bonded shield (Figure 2) and then the attenuation due to propagation loss from an exposed center conductor, if one is present (Figure 3). The attenuation factors are compared and the lower of the two is used.

Experimental verification of this methodology is depicted in Figure 4. Curve 3 of this figure depicts the measured S.E. of RG-58C/U coaxial cable with an exposed center conductor one meter from the receiver port. Superimposed on this figure is the measured S.E. of the cable without an exposed center conductor (curve 1) and the measured attenuation along a one meter length of RG-58C/U (curve 2). As can be seen from the figure, curve 3 follows the lower of curve 1 or curve 2. This result supports the attenuation model selected for use in IEMCAP. Similar sets of attenuation models were developed for double shielded cables and shielded twisted pairs.

Figure 3. Transmission Loss for RG-58C/U

Figure 4. Frequency Dependent Attenuation for Field-to-Wire Coupling Mechanisms

Conclusion

A number of cable shielding effectiveness measurements were conducted in a mode-tuned reverberation chamber to determine what parameters most influence S.E. The experimental results support an empirical model for inclusion in IEMCAP that is dependent on cable type and cable termination condition. The model is very sensitive to the existence and location of an exposed center conductor or pigtail.

References

- [1] P. Griffin, A. McMahon, G. Capraro, S. Macris, and J. Riccardi, "SHF/EHF Field-to-Wire Coupling Models," RADC-TR-88-151, Final Technical Report, Rome Air Development Center, July 1988.
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